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Clambidae: *Acalyptomerus*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus infumatus*

Remnant of claval line present. CuP reduced. AA 3+4 clearly added to remigium.
Anal lobe starts at anal fold.

Scirtidae: *Pseudomicrocara*

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Scirtidae: *Pseudomiracara*

Scirtidae: *Pseudomicrocara*

Clambidae: *Acalyptomerus*

Clambidae: *Calyptomerus*

Clambidae: *Sphaerothorax tasmani*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus infumatus*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus infumatus*

Eucinetidae: *Eucinetus* sp.

Scirtidae: *Macrohelodes*

9mm

CuP and claval line reduced

Scirtidae: *Pseudomicrocara*

Scirtidae: *Pseudomiracara*

Dascillidae: *Notodascillus* sp.

Dascillidae: *Notodascillus* sp.

Dascillidae: *Notodascillus* sp.

Dascyllidae: *Dascyllus* sp.

Fig. #. Group 11. RHIPICERIDAE

Sandalus sp.

TL (mm)	TL/EW	APF/TL	APF/GW
13.62	2.42	0.24	0.56

Buprestidae: *Schizopus* sp.

Byrrhidae: *Byrrhus* sp.

Coleoptera apomorphies in hind wing articulation:

AX-PC & C (tegula) reduced; B-R partly membranized; F-M subdivided; B-M large, connected with B-Cu; AX-Cu (3Ax) small, sutured, and often fragmented; AX-Cu fused with F-Cu; F-Cu fused with FA

Byrrhidae: *Byrrhus* sp.

Byrrhidae: *Byrrhus* sp.

Psephenidae: *Sclerocyphon* sp.

Psephenidae: *Sclerocyplon* sp.

Psephenidae: *Sclerocyphon* sp.

Philodactylidae: *Byrrocryptis variegatus*

Ptilodactylidae: *Byrrocryptus variegatus*

DORSAL

VENTRAL